

DMP4NFDI Service Cooperation Model

For the collaboration between the basic service DMP4NFDI of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and the NFDI consortia.

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General Information and Objectives

This DMP4NFDI Service Cooperation Model (SCM) outlines the collaboration between the basic service under development DMP4NFDI of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and the NFDI consortia. This first version provides clear guidance on the support provided by the basic service and the responsibilities of the consortia. It is based on the work of DMP4NFDI in the initialisation phase and will be further developed in exchange with the consortia.

The DMP4NFDI SCM addresses those in the NFDI consortia who are responsible for data management plans (DMPs), software management plans (SMPs) or similar concepts. The document builds the foundation for further service development and clarification of technical requirements and support levels, based on the exchange between the NFDI consortia and DMP4NFDI. The Service Level Agreement concept developed by the Hessian Research Data Infrastructures (HeFDI) was used as a model.¹

To facilitate the effective usage and implementation of DMPs and SMPs across the NFDI consortia, DMP4NFDI hosts a multi-tenant instance of the open source tool Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO). Hosting RDMO clients for the consortia enables cross-consortia collaborative work on catalogues and further service integration. In addition, the basic service develops the NFDI DMP Template Framework that facilitates the creation of interoperable and standardised templates in RDMO. Furthermore, DMP4NFDI supports the consortia by offering training, providing materials as Open Educational Resources (OER), as well as relevant guidelines and documentation.

These measures aim to provide discipline-specific DMP/SMP templates in standardised, machine-readable and interoperable formats. They facilitate communication between all stakeholders and services involved in a data management process.

The development of the basic service DMP4NFDI is supported by the Base4NFDI initiative, which was launched in 2023. Base4NFDI establishes a framework for the development of cross-disciplinary basic services to foster FAIR practices and meet the research data management needs of the scientific community within and beyond the NFDI. Base4NFDI fosters synergies between the NFDI consortia by supporting the development and consolidation of the basic services in three phases: initialisation, integration and ramp-up. The initiative provides funding and support for the development of these services.

¹ Brand et al. (2022).

Support Levels

This SCM is divided into three support levels, serving as a guideline for the cooperation between DMP4NFDI and the NFDI consortia. The consortia are responsible for the provision of first-level support, which includes the direct support of their communities in the use of DMPs, SMPs and RDMO. DMP4NFDI is responsible for tool hosting and second and third-level support, providing technical assistance, standardisation, training, implementation and support on DMP/SMP template development, RDMO use and community outreach activities.

Fig. 1: Overview support levels and responsibilities

First-Level Support

First-level support is provided by the NFDI consortia. It includes direct assistance of their communities and the cooperation with DMP4NFDI. Key tasks are fostering contact with their communities and providing the necessary resources for community-specific adaptation of DMP/SMP templates and materials in cooperation with DMP4NFDI.

First-Level Support Overview

- Offers community support
- Provides contact persons and defines responsibilities
- Adapts and develops discipline-specific templates
- Provides feedback to improve the service

Community Support

The consortia take an active role in working with DMP4NFDI and act as a direct point of contact for their community (e.g. through helpdesks). They advise and support researchers in the use of DMPs, SMPs and tools such as RDMO. At the same time, they are responsible for community outreach activities such as workshops or training sessions to foster adoption and further establish DMPs and SMPs in their community.

RDMO Contact Persons and Responsibilities

Regarding RDMO-Hosting, the consortia provide contact persons for login or community-AAI (authentication and authorisation infrastructure for consortium access), customisation of their RDMO client's frontend-design, and the general website contents. They name consortia staff responsible for DMP support and template development who should receive the corresponding rights in RDMO (managers/editors). They also report any changes. In order to successfully integrate RDMO into the consortia's service portfolio, e.g. through the development of plug-ins, the consortia will need to plan for additional personnel resources, depending on the complexity of the task. The implementation will be carried out together with third-level support.

Adaptation and Development of Discipline-Specific Templates

The consortia allocate time and human resources for the adaptation or development of discipline-specific DMP or SMP templates in RDMO. DMP4NFDI will support the development process (see Second-Level Support), but outreach and adding discipline-specific content requires the assistance of personnel with the necessary scientific background and knowledge of the community.

Feedback & Jour Fixe

The consortia provide feedback to improve the NFDI DMP Template Framework. They regularly participate in training workshops and monthly support Jour-Fixes organised by DMP4NFDI to exchange feedback and clarify open questions.

Second-Level Support

Second-level support is provided by the DMP4NFDI service. Its main focus is to support NFDI consortia in template development, use of RDMO, and community outreach activities. Training materials and documentation will be made available for the first-level support to use.

Second-Level Support Overview

- Provides a support infrastructure for NFDI consortia
- Develops and maintains the NFDI DMP Template Framework
- Offers support for template development and community outreach activities
- Provides trainings and documentation

Support Infrastructure

DMP4NFDI provides support structures including a website with documentation, a mailing list serving as the primary point of contact for consortia using the basic service, and OpenProject as a ticket system. To ensure efficient communication, monthly Jour-Fixes offer a platform to answer questions, share ideas, explore potential collaborations, identify needs and give feedback to the basic service.

NFDI DMP Template Framework

DMP4NFDI is responsible for developing and maintaining the NFDI DMP Template Framework to create interoperable and standardised templates for DMPs and SMPs. The framework contains general questions, defines a standardised DMP vocabulary (RDMO attributes) for the NFDI and rules to add compatible community-specific modules. DMP4NFDI will ensure interoperability of the framework with international initiatives (EOSC, RDA) by contributing to them.

Template Development and Support

The basic service also provides advice and support to consortia in using RDMO for the creation of catalogues, tailoring them to the needs of their communities, and aligning them with the developed framework. Depending on the status of the consortia templates and their previous experience with RDMO, assistance may consist of transferring textual templates into RDMO or revising existing RDMO templates and adapting them to the structure of the framework. Consortia may also take the individual steps themselves, receiving advice from DMP4NFDI in the process.

Trainings

The basic service offers train-the-trainer workshops and capacity building on DMPs, SMPs, and RDMO for the consortia. Training materials will be made available and regularly adapted to the needs of the consortia.

Community Outreach

DMP4NFDI actively supports the consortia in planning and implementing community outreach activities. In addition, regular updates on developments, best practices and success stories will be made available on the DMP4NFDI website or via the NFDI Rocket.Chat instance. A knowledge base of service documentation, how-tos, FAQs and best practices will be provided on the website to ensure a low threshold for the use of the service.

Third-Level Support

Third-level support is provided by DMP4NFDI. Core tasks include technical operation, maintenance and support of RDMO for the consortia, and exchange with the RDMO community regarding further development of the software.

Third-Level Support Overview

- Provides RDMO hosting
- Facilitates the integration of RDMO with other tools and services provided by the NFDI consortia
- Engages and cooperates with the RDMO community

RDMO Hosting

DMP4NFDI hosts a multi-tenant RDMO instance with customisable clients for the consortia. This includes access management, roles and rights management, server management and maintenance, and general technical support for the consortia clients.

Integration of RDMO with NFDI Service Portfolio

The basic service fosters the integration of RDMO with other tools and services provided by the NFDI or the NFDI consortia. DMP4NFDI assists the consortia in leveraging the RDMO API for service integration, develops plug-ins, and generally supports connecting RDMO to services.

Exchange with RDMO Community

RDMO is developed by an Open Source community in which DMP4NFDI is actively involved. The basic service collects feedback, bugs and requirements from the consortia for further RDMO development and contributes them to the general RDMO roadmap.

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References

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